

**EFFECTS OF HOT-WATER AND STEAM BLANCHING OF
SLICED POTATO (var. Jelly) ON POLYPHENOL OXIDASE
ACTIVITY**

Journal:	<i>International Journal of Food Science and Technology</i>
Manuscript ID	Draft
Manuscript Type:	Original Manuscript
Date Submitted by the Author:	n/a
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Keywords:	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i> L., thermal treatment, PPO, inactivation kinetic, substrate specificity, transition state

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ABSTRACT

The worldwide potato production is considered the fourth-most important food sector due to the increasing use of potatoes as raw materials for high-convenience food. Colour is a crucial quality attribute in fresh-cut potatoes, and enzymatic browning, due to polyphenols oxidase (PPO), is related to unacceptability by consumer. Among additives used to minimize discoloration, sulphites are very common, but affected by health-related hazards and marketing issues. Viable alternatives are thermal treatments, used to inactivate enzymes and improve product shelf-life. In this study, the efficacy of hot-water and steam blanching from 80 to 90°C, used to inactivate PPO in 1-cm potato slices, was evaluated in terms of inactivation kinetic, substrate specificity and transition state parameters. In general, all treatments inactivated PPO and reduced its kinetic efficiency. In detail, results from thermal inactivation kinetic promoted hot-water blanching at 90°C for approx. 2 min as the fastest treatment to obtain colour-stable potato slices.

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For Peer Review

a Sample preparation

b Blanching treatments

c Catalytic efficiency of PPO enzyme

d Thermodynamic analysis

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3 **EFFECTS OF HOT-WATER AND STEAM BLANCHING OF SLICED POTATO (var.**
4 **Jelly) ON POLYPHENOL OXIDASE ACTIVITY**
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31 **1.0 INTRODUCTION**
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33 During the recent years, potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) world production has largely increased
34 and nowadays is considered the fourth-most important food sector with a worldwide consumption
35 of 230 mil tonnes per year (Devaux *et al.*, 2014; FAOSTAT, 2017). In this context, the market
36 demand of fresh-cut, dried, frozen and fried potatoes grown in order to respond to the increasing
37 consumers demand of high-convenience food.
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43 Processing ability and final quality of potato products, as many other processed fruit and
44 vegetables, are mainly affected by pre-harvest (e.g. genotype) and post-harvest factors (e.g.
45 processing operations), which may have an impact on product susceptibility to nutritional and
46 sensorial losses (Rolle and Chism, 1987; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, preservation methods
47 that enhance food stability by delaying physicochemical, biochemical and microbiological spoilage
48 affect market values of perishable commodities (Moschetti *et al.*, 2017, 2018).
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3 Colour and appearance of cut potato are crucial quality attributes; in fact, discoloration due to
4 enzymatic browning is one of the main reasons for unacceptability by consumer. In addition,
5 enzymatic browning also deteriorates nutritional values since phenols are oxidized to *o*-quinones,
6 which are highly reactive with amino acids, proteins, and other phenols, undergoing irreversible
7 brown colour development (Ali *et al.*, 2016). In general, the most important factors which
8 determine the rate of enzymatic browning in cut potato are oxidative enzyme activity (i.e.
9 polyphenol oxidase, PPO), oxygen and phenols availability (i.e. chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid,
10 gallic acid and protocatechuic acid), as well as pH, temperature and water activity of the reaction
11 medium (Martinez and Whitaker, 1995a; Hou *et al.*, 2014). Thus, understanding the enzymatic
12 oxidative processes is fundamental to (1) select and tune the proper treatment for minimizing the
13 occurrence of browning reactions in the after-cutting stages (i.e. washing, sorting, drying, freezing,
14 frying, packaging, storage, transportation, etc.), (2) avoid food waste and (3) maintain viability of
15 producers and exporters (He and Luo, 2007).

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31 Various approaches have been extensively studied to minimize the occurrence of enzymatic
32 browning. These methods focus on the use of cultivar selection, appropriate cutting operations,
33 ozone treatment, blanching (e.g. hot-water, steam, etc.), additives (e.g. antioxidants, plant extracts,
34 calcium salts, coatings, etc.), controlled atmosphere, refrigeration, packaging selection, etc. (Angós
35 *et al.*, 2008; Erturk and Picha, 2008; Cabezas-Serrano *et al.*, 2009; Hou *et al.*, 2014; Tsouvaltzis and
36 Brecht, 2017). The most common additives used for quality maintenance of cut potatoes are
37 sulphites, which are inexpensive and very effective against browning but affected by off-flavour
38 development as well as health hazard (e.g. bronchial asthma) and marketing issues. In fact, sulphites
39 cause allergic reactions and, consequently, are subjected to government regulation in several
40 countries. Alternatively, blanching is frequently used prior frying, drying or freezing of cut potatoes
41 because its capability of inactivating enzymes, and then improving appearance, processability and
42 shelf-life of products (Wang *et al.*, 2017). However, heat treatment may also lead to quality loss and
43 therefore it must be performed for the minimum time required to completely deactivate deleterious

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3 enzymes (Anthon and Barrett, 2002). Consequently, the duration of heat treatments is often
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5 monitored using an indicator enzyme. Blanching methods includes hot water (i.e. solution
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7 containing or not acids and/or salts), steam, microwave, infrared, ohmic and radio frequency
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9 heating (Zhang *et al.*, 2018).
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11 While research on potato antibrowning treatments is widely reported, little insight is available
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13 on thermal inactivation of PPO enzyme in potato slices, and studies of its thermal stability and
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15 inactivation energy during blanching are poor or totally lacking. Therefore, the objective of this
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17 research was to report detailed characterization data for PPO enzyme in potato slices subjected to
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19 hot-water and steam blanching. The results of the present work are a contribution to the studies on
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21 reducing enzymatic browning of cut potato by heat-inactivation.
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26 **2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

27 *2.1 Samples preparation*

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30 Potato tubers (*Solanum tuberosum* L. var. Jelly) were provided by an Italian fresh-cut processor
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32 (CO.P.A.VIT., Acquapendente, Italy), and immediately stored at $14\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ until processing. Tubers
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34 sampling was performed by selecting sound potatoes, with uniform size.
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38 Potato tubers were washed in chlorinated water (sodium hypochlorite, NaClO 200 ppm) for 3
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40 min, peeled and cut into slices (1-cm thick and 1.2-cm diameter; corresponding to approx. 10 ± 0.1
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42 g) using an electric stainless-steel food slicer mod. 380 (ALA2000, Treviso, Italy). Finally, potato
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44 slices were held in chlorinated water (NaClO 50 ppm) for 3 min and then gently dried by hand with
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46 cheesecloth (Fig. 1a). Samples were visually evaluated and only slices free from decay and/or
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48 blemishes were used in the experimentation.
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50 *2.3 Blanching treatments*

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52 Two different blanching methods were tested: (1) hot-water and (2) steam blanching. Both
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54 blanching methods were conducted at 80 and 90 °C for 0 to 10 min of heating on the basis of
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56 screening results obtained from tests conducted in a range from 60 to 90 °C. Blanching treatments
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3 at temperature lower than 80°C were not reported due to a treatment time exceeding more than 10
4 min to reach the *D*-value (or decimal reduction time). In fact, blanching tests were set up to ensure a
5 polyphenol oxidase inactivation of 90% in a reasonable treatment time. This level of inactivation
6 was fixed as threshold in order to allow the produce to become stable and, thus, in line with
7 industrial requirements (Moscetti *et al.*, 2017, 2018). The experimental plan is reported in Table 1.
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13 Both hot-water and steam blanching treatments were performed in a temperature-controlled
14 water bath (Astor 800D, Astori Tecnica, Brescia, Italy) (Fig. 1b and 1c, respectively). Regarding the
15 steam blanching, it consisted in injecting steam through a chamber in which potato slices were
16 placed. Steam temperature was monitored with a 10-k Ω thermistor coupled to an Arduino Micro
17 board, calibrated and validated in a temperature range of 20-90 °C (Fig. 2).
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24 After blanching treatment, samples were immediately cooled for 3 min in ice-water and the
25 residual PPO enzymatic activity was evaluated.
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28 2.3 Polyphenol oxidase activity

29 2.3.1 Enzyme extraction

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32 Enzyme extraction was carried out in accordance with Massantini *et al.* (2009). Fresh-cut potato
33 samples were collected, frozen with liquid nitrogen and then immediately grinded into frozen
34 powder by an analytic mill (IKA A11 basic; IKA Labortechnik, Staufen, Germany). Ten grams of
35 potato powder were homogenized with 10 mL of chilled phosphate buffer saline solution (PBS, 0.1
36 M, pH 7.2) containing 1.5% (w/v) of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPP) and 0.1% of Triton X-100.
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38 The mixture was centrifuged at 12,000 \times g for 20 min at 4 \pm 0.5°C, the supernatant was collected and
39 stored at 4 \pm 1°C prior to the enzymatic assay.
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48 2.3.2 Enzyme activity measurement

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50 Polyphenol oxidase (PPO) activity was measured by following the method of Moscetti *et al.*
51 (2012) with slight modifications. The assay was performed using an UV-Vis scanning
52 spectrophotometer (Lambda 25; PerkinElmer, Massachusetts, United States). Changes in the
53 absorbance at 420 nm were monitored for 2 min upon oxidation of the substrates catalysed by the
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enzyme. Catechol (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, United States) was used as substrate. The final reaction mixture contained 0.2 mL of crude enzyme, 1.5 mL of PBS (0.1 M, pH 7.2), 0.15 mL of catechol 1 M and 1.2 mL of distilled water. One unit of enzyme activity (U) was defined as an increase in absorbance of 0.001 min^{-1} . Dry matter was assessed following the official method 'Dry Matter on Oven Drying'—AOAC 934.01 (Horwitz, 2005) and then the PPO enzymatic activity was expressed on dry weight basis. Enzyme activity was measured in triplicate.

2.3.3 Thermal inactivation kinetic

The rate constant for first-order inactivation (k) was computed from the slope of the linear regression of natural log of residual activity versus time of thermal treatment, according to Eq. 1.

$$\ln \frac{V_t}{V_0} = -kt, \quad (1)$$

where V_0 is the initial enzyme activity (U), t is the time of heating (min), V_t is the activity after heating for time t , and k is the inactivation rate constant (min^{-1}). The nonlinear (weighted) least-squares algorithm was used to estimate the optimal k -value of the nonlinear inactivation model. Model performances were evaluated in terms of coefficient of determination (R^2) and Root Mean Squared Errors (RMSE).

The inactivation time was computed as D -value (or decimal reduction time), which is the treatment time required to reduce the enzyme activity to at least 0.1 (i.e. 10%) of its original value, according to Eq. 2.

$$D = \frac{2.303}{k}, \quad (2)$$

Finally, both Z -value and the half-life time ($t_{1/2}$) were computed, which are defined as the number of degrees temperature needed to be increased in order to achieve a 1 \log_{10} reduction in the D -value and the time required for the enzyme activity to reduce to 50% its initial value, respectively.

2.3.4 Substrate specificity

The inhibition type of thermal processing on PPO activity was determined for both hot-water and steam blanching at 80 and 90 °C. The reaction mixture consisted of 9 different concentrations of catechol ranging from 0.01 to 1 M and 0.2 ml of the crude enzyme. Results were plotted as a Lineweaver-Burk plot, according to Eqs. 3 and 4.

$$V = \frac{V_{max}[S]}{K_m + [S]}, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{V} = \frac{K_m}{V_{max}} \frac{1}{[S]} + \frac{1}{V_{max}}, \quad (4)$$

where V is the reaction rate (U gDW^{-1}), K_m is the Michaelis-Menten constant expressed as molar concentration (M), V_{max} is the maximum reaction rate ($\text{U gDW}^{-1} \text{M}^{-1}$) and $[S]$ is the catechol concentration (M). The catalytic efficiency was calculated as $V_{max} K_m^{-1}$ ratio.

2.3.5 Transition state parameters

The inactivation kinetic (k) dependence from the temperature and the activation energy (ΔE^\ddagger) were both determined using the Arrhenius's law (Eq. 5).

$$\ln(k) = \ln(k_{ref}) - \frac{\Delta E^\ddagger}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}} \right), \quad (5)$$

where k_{ref} is the inactivation rate at the reference temperature (T_{ref}) and R is the universal gas constant ($8.3144 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). By establishing k and ΔE^\ddagger values, it is possible to obtain transition state parameters according to absolute reaction rate theory (Forsyth *et al.*, 1999). Consequently, changes in the activation enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger), activation Gibbs free energy (ΔG^\ddagger), activation entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) and normalised activation entropy ($-T\Delta S^\ddagger$) for enzyme heat-inactivation were determined using Eqs. 6-8.

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta E^\ddagger - RT, \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = -RT \ln \frac{kh}{K_B T}, \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \frac{(\Delta H^\ddagger - \Delta G^\ddagger)}{T}, \quad (8)$$

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3 where K_B is the Boltzmann's constant ($1.3806 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$), h is the Planck's constant (6.6262
4 $10^{-34} \text{ J s}^{-1}$), and k is the inactivation rate constant (s^{-1}) at the studied temperature. Finally, the
5 isokinetic temperature was graphically determined by using the criterion proposed by Exner (1970).
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8 9 *2.4 Statistical analysis*

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11 Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate statistical differences
12 among factors. The Tukey's pairwise comparison method was performed and the Honestly
13 Significant Difference (HSD) was calculated for an appropriate level of interaction ($P \leq 0.05$)
14 (Montgomery, 2001). Results were reported as the mean and standard error of the mean.
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16 Lineweaver Burk and velocity substrate profile were computed using Matlab software R2015a.
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18 Data handling and ANOVA were both performed using R v3.2.4 software in combination with
19 'agricolae' v1.2-3 R-package (CRAN, 2017).
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29 **3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

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31 Potato slices were treated with hot-water and steam blanching; the impact of each treatment
32 as PPO enzyme inactivator was investigated by evaluating non-linear first-order inactivation
33 kinetic, substrate specificity and transition state parameters.
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36 37 *3.1 Thermal inactivation kinetic*

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39 The effect of thermal treatment on potato slices was evaluated for both hot-water and steam
40 blanching over the pre-established range of temperature (i.e. 80 and 90°C) (Table 2), which was
41 chosen on the basis of the well-known potato heat-injury resistance (Yemenicioğlu, 2002). To
42 monitor the thermal treatment, PPO was used as indicator enzyme due to its relationship with
43 enzymatic browning (Martinez and Whitaker, 1995b).
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50 Inactivation kinetics was determined through semi-log plot of residual PPO activity versus
51 time. Results showed excellent linear fits ($R = -0.97 \div -0.99$), and the straight lines extrapolated back
52 to a common point for all treatments, consistent with the inactivation occurring by first-order
53 kinetics (Fig. 3a). Moreover, investigation through non-linear least square regression demonstrated
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3 that the non-linear first-order kinetic well fits the process over the heating time (Fig. 3b). Model
4 showed that half the total of PPO activity was rapidly inactivated in less than 1 min in all treatments
5 except for the steam blanching at 80°C, which showed a half-life time ($t_{1/2}$) of 1.240 min. In fact,
6 the magnitude of non-linearity observed was greater during approx. 1 min of treatment. Thus, in our
7 experimentation, the observed rapid loss of PPO activity seemed to be related with a simple first-
8 order model that assumed two isoforms of the enzyme. The existence of labile and resistant
9 isoforms of PPO was already demonstrated in various fruit and vegetables (Nozue *et al.*, 1998; Ho,
10 1999; Ayaz *et al.*, 2008); however, different patterns of PPO isoforms were found in potato tubers
11 among cultivars and during the time-course of storage (Marri *et al.*, 2003). These multiple isoforms
12 seems to be responsible for complex inactivation kinetics at heating temperature lower than 70°C,
13 as already observed by Anthon & Barrett (2002).
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26 Although all heat-inactivation processes reached the inactivation threshold (i.e. decimal
27 reduction time, D -value), considerably faster reduction in PPO activity was obtained by treatments
28 at 90°C, which showed a faster inactivation rate constant ($k = 1.057 \text{ min}^{-1}$) in comparison with the
29 80°C ones ($k = 0.682 \text{ min}^{-1}$). Moreover, the k constant revealed the minor effectiveness of steam
30 blanching in reducing PPO activity. In fact, assuming the same temperature of treatment, hot-water
31 blanching always overwhelmed steam blanching in terms of D -value. Specifically, the lowest D -
32 value among treatments was achieved by hot-water blanching at 90°C for 1.943 min of dipping.
33 Regarding the Z -value, which is the temperature needed to vary D -value one log-unit, it was
34 smallest in steam treatment. This indicates that a variation in steam temperature affected more
35 intensely the stability of PPO activity in potato slices.
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48 Finally, considering that evaluation of typical issues from both steam blanching (i.e. non-
49 uniform blanching effect) and hot-water blanching (i.e. loss of flavours and nutrients such as
50 vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates, sugars, phenols and proteins caused mainly by leaching and/or
51 diffusion) (Xiao *et al.*, 2017) were not part of the present study, results from thermal inactivation
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kinetic allows to speculate that hot-water blanching at 90°C for approx. 2 min may be considered as the most adequate treatment in order to obtain colour-stable potato slices of 1-cm thickness.

3.2 Effect of blanching on substrate specificity

PPO activity showed a typical Michaelis-Menten profile in all tests. Kinetic parameters were calculated from the Lineweaver-Burk double reciprocal plot (Fig. 4a) and in all cases regressions were linear, showing coefficient of determination ranging from 0.98 to 0.99. Results were reported in Tab. 3. The K_m values showed that potato PPO had lower affinity for the substrate (i.e. catechol) when samples were subjected to hot-water blanching. In fact, PPO enzyme became kinetically less reactive in potato slices blanched in hot-water. Regarding V_{max} value (Fig. 4b), which is positively related to the enzyme concentration, it significantly dropped in all heating treatments. In addition, the catalytic efficiency (i.e. $V_{max} K_m^{-1}$) provided additional useful information to establish which was the most performing treatment in reducing enzyme efficiency. Thus, the lowest $V_{max} K_m^{-1}$ value corresponded to the hot-water blanching, then followed by the steam treatment, while, as expected, the control was characterised by the highest catalytic efficiency. Results did not show any impact of treatment temperature on the $V_{max} K_m^{-1}$ value. Finally, it is possible to assert that both hot-water and steam blanching not only inactivated part of the enzyme, but also affected the kinetic efficiency of the remaining PPO. However, the overall assumption is that hot-water blanching was more effective in reducing substrate specificity of potato's PPO.

3.3 Transition state parameters

The activation energy of PPO inactivation (ΔE^\ddagger) for both hot-water and steam blanching treatments is reported in Tab. 4. In general, the low ΔE^\ddagger values highlighted the fragility of the potato PPO enzyme and then its easiness to be inactivated by heat exposure, regardless the blanching factor. The different type of thermal treatment significantly affected the amount of activation energy required. In fact, hot-water blanching acted by lowering the ΔE^\ddagger and then showed a slightly superior effectiveness in inactivating the PPO in comparison with the steam treatment. In addition, results necessarily mean that the inactivation process in steam treatment was more temperature dependent

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3 than in hot-water, and that the inactivation process through steam blanching run very slowly at low
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5 temperature, but relatively fast at high temperatures.

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7 ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ are enthalpy, entropy and normalised entropy of activation for transition
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9 state reaction, respectively. ΔH^\ddagger represents the difference in energy between ground state and
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11 transition state in the potato PPO inactivation process, while both ΔS^\ddagger and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ correspond to the
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13 change in entropy when the enzyme changes from its initial state to transition state. Those
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15 parameters provide useful information about the mechanism for enzyme inactivation, such as the
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17 amount of non-covalent bonds broken and the net enzyme/solvent disorder change related with the
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19 transition state reaction (Ortega *et al.*, 2004).

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22 From Tab. 4, it is showed how higher ΔH^\ddagger values corresponded to greater amounts of
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24 energy required to form the transition state, while negative ΔS^\ddagger (or positive $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$) values suggested
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26 conglomeration of partially unfolded enzymes (Owusu and Bertholon, 1993), which were
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28 predominantly produced during protein exposure to high temperature (Dannenbergh and Kessler,
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30 1988). In addition, ΔH^\ddagger and $\Delta S^\ddagger/-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ gave information about enthalpic and/or entropic heat-
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32 resistance of potato PPO enzyme. Specifically, enthalpic stabilisation was referred to a positive ΔH^\ddagger
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34 value and entropic stabilisation occurred when ΔS^\ddagger was negative (or $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ was positive). According
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36 to the obtained results, steam blanching was characterized by the highest ΔH^\ddagger value; consequently, it
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38 required more energy than hot-water treatment to reach the transition state and then to unfold the
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40 PPO enzyme. Moreover, both hot-water and steam treatments showed enthalpic and entropic
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42 stabilisations, as well as possible aggregation of partially unfolded enzyme molecules. Finally, the
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44 interaction of 'blanching \times temperature' had significant effect on activating Gibbs free energy,
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46 which tended to increase when blanching was carried out with steam and/or using a 90-°C
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48 blanching temperature. Despite this, all ΔG^\ddagger were at the order of magnitude expected for protein
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50 denaturation.
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55 Fig. 5 shows that the temperature dependence of the k -value was adequately described by
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57 the Arrhenius equation. From those data, an isokinetic temperature (i.e. the temperature at which all
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3 inactivation processes proceed at the same rate) of 103.33°C was also computed. Results indicated
4 that the sensitivity of the k -value towards temperature variations was bigger in steam blanching than
5 in hot-water treatment. However, it also meant that, below the isokinetic temperature, PPO was
6 more stable in steam than in hot-water. By way of explanation, under the tested conditions, the
7 thermal inactivation of potato PPO was enhanced by the hot-water treatment.
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13 14 15 **4.0 CONCLUSIONS**

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18 In this study, the potential of both hot-water and steam blanching at 80 and 90°C as
19 antibrowning treatments for potato slices (1-cm thick) was evaluated through a detailed
20 characterization of PPO enzyme activity. For this purpose, the effectiveness of each treatment was
21 described by analysing the inactivation kinetic of PPO, the changes in enzyme substrate specificity
22 after treatment, and the transition state parameters of each thermal process. The results showed that
23 both thermal treatments can efficiently inactivate potato PPO in less than 5 min. However, although
24 all thermal treatments showed their feasibility in reducing the tendency of browning in minimally
25 processed potatoes, type and temperature of treatment significantly affected the inactivation rate
26 constant and stability of enzyme ($P \leq 0.05$). Consistent with blanching temperature, hot-water
27 enhanced thermal inactivation of PPO and was always faster than steam in reducing PPO activity to
28 at least 10% of its original value. Below the isokinetic temperature (i.e. 103.33°C) PPO was more
29 stable in steam than in hot-water. In fact, results showed that steam blanching required more energy
30 than hot-water treatment to reach the transition state and then to unfold the PPO enzyme. Despite
31 this, all treatments were able to inactivate part of the enzyme and reduce the kinetic efficiency of
32 remaining PPO.
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50 Finally, the present study provides valuable information in order to understand the effect of
51 both hot-water and steam blanching treatments at 80 and 90°C on the PPO enzyme stability.
52 However, in our opinion, further investigations should be performed with the aim of comparing
53 both treatments on the basis of their impact on both sensorial and nutritional quality of potato slices.
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5.0 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge CORE Organic Plus consortium (Coordination of European Transnational Research in Organic Food and Farming System, ERA-NET action) and Mipaaf (Ministero delle politiche agricole alimentari e forestali - Italy) for financial support through the SusOrganic project titled: 'Development of quality standards and optimized processing methods for organic produce' (Nr: 2814OE006). Moreover, our sincere thanks to [1] the CO.P.A.VIT. (Acquapendente, Latium region, Italy) for the potato samples and [2] Gianpaolo Moschetti for the English language revision of the manuscript.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

- Figure 1.** *Simplified step-by-step representation of (a) sample preparation, (b) hot-water blanching and (c) steam blanching procedures.*
- Figure 2.** *Linear regression plot (a) and prediction error plot (b) of Y-measured (reference temperature) versus Y-predicted (predicted temperature) and Y-measured versus prediction error, respectively, from data obtained by using a digital thermometer based on the Arduino microcontroller.*
- Figure 3.** *Semi-log (a) and non-linear (b) first-order plots for the heat inactivation of potato slices' polyphenol oxidase in hot-water at 90°C. Half-life time ($t_{1/2}$) and decimal reduction time (D-value) are treatment times required to reduce the residual polyphenol oxidase activity to at least 0.5 and 0.1, respectively*
- Figure 4.** *Lineweaver-Burk double reciprocal plot (a) and velocity substrate profile (b) for polyphenol oxidase extract from control (blue line) and blanching (red line, i.e. hot-water at 90°C) samples. K_m = Michaelis constant; V_{max} = maximum velocity.*
- Figure 5.** *Temperature dependence of the k-values for thermal inactivation of PPO subjected to hot-water and steam blanching.*

A) SAMPLE PREPARATION

B) HOT-WATER BLANCHING

C) STEAM BLANCHING

Figure 1

199x199mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2

83x35mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3

170x288mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 4

99x49mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 5

82x73mm (300 x 300 DPI)

TABLE CAPTIONS

Table 1. *Experimental design for the hot-water and the steam blanching treatments. HW - hot-water blanching; ST – Steam blanching*

Table 2. *Summary of the main effects of blanching and temperature on thermal inactivation parameters. Mean values (\pm st.dev.) belonging to the same factor without common letters are statistically different according to HSD ($P \leq 0.05$).*

Table 3. *Summary of the main effects of thermal treatment on kinetic parameters. Mean values (\pm st.dev.) without common letters are statistically different according to HSD ($P \leq 0.05$).*

Table 4. *Summary of the main effects of blanching and temperature on activation energy, activation enthalpy, activation Gibbs free energy, activation entropy and normalised activation entropy change values. Mean values (\pm st. dev.) belonging to the same factor without common letters are statistically different according to HSD ($P \leq 0.05$).*

TABLE 1

Hot-water blanching			Steam blanching		
ID	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	ID	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)
HW-80-0	80	0.00	ST-80-0	80	0.00
HW-80-1	80	0.50	ST-80-1	80	0.50
HW-80-2	80	1.00	ST-80-2	80	1.00
HW-80-3	80	1.50	ST-80-3	80	1.50
HW-80-4	80	2.00	ST-80-4	80	2.00
HW-80-5	80	3.00	ST-80-5	80	3.00
HW-80-6	80	5.00	ST-80-6	80	5.00
HW-80-7	80	10.00	ST-80-7	80	10.00
HW-90-0	90	0.00	ST-90-0	90	0.00
HW-90-1	90	0.25	ST-90-1	90	0.25
HW-90-2	90	0.50	ST-90-2	90	0.50
HW-90-3	90	0.75	ST-90-3	90	0.75
HW-90-4	90	1.00	ST-90-4	90	1.00
HW-90-5	90	1.50	ST-90-5	90	1.50
HW-90-6	90	2.00	ST-90-6	90	2.00
HW-90-7	90	3.00	ST-90-7	90	2.50
			ST-90-8	90	3.00
			ST-90-9	90	5.00

Review

TABLE 2

Factors	k^a (min ⁻¹)	$t_{1/2}^b$ (min)	D^c (min)	Z^d (°C)
Blanching (B)				
Water	0.996 ± 0.087 a	0.725 ± 0.062	2.403 ± 0.208	60.66 ± 5.99 a
Steam	0.742 ± 0.083 b	0.995 ± 0.110	3.307 ± 0.366	45.68 ± 1.23 b
<i>Pr</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.01
<i>HSD</i>	0.065	-	-	13.04
Temperature (T)				
80°C (353.15°K)	0.682 ± 0.056 b	1.052 ± 0.085	3.493 ± 0.283	
90°C (363.15°K)	1.057 ± 0.060 a	0.668 ± 0.038	2.217 ± 0.126	
<i>Pr</i>	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	
<i>HSD</i>	0.065	-	-	
Blanching (B) x Temperature (T)				
Water 80°C (353.15°K)	0.805 ± 0.015	0.863 ± 0.015 b	2.863 ± 0.052 b	
Water 90°C (363.15°K)	1.187 ± 0.030	0.587 ± 0.013 d	1.943 ± 0.047 d	
Steam 80°C (353.15°K)	0.558 ± 0.005	1.240 ± 0.012 a	4.123 ± 0.035 a	
Steam 90°C (363.15°K)	0.926 ± 0.018	0.750 ± 0.015 c	2.490 ± 0.053 c	
<i>Pr</i>	ns	< 0.001	< 0.001	
<i>HSD</i>	-	0.085	0.085	

^a k , first-order reaction rate constant; ^b $t_{1/2}$, half-life time; ^c D , decimal reduction time, ^d Z , thermal resistance constant.

TABLE 3

Factor	K_m^a (M)	V_{max}^b (U gDW ⁻¹)	$V_{max} K_m^{-1c}$ (U gDW ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)
Control	0.133 ± 0.025 ab	87.06 ± 4.81 a	708.10 ± 162.23 a
Hot-water @ 80°C	0.213 ± 0.027 a	37.93 ± 3.14 c	180.60 ± 9.44 b
Hot-water @ 90°C	0.208 ± 0.003 a	52.19 ± 0.84 b	251.00 ± 0.98 b
Steam @ 80°C	0.109 ± 0.009 b	48.50 ± 0.89 bc	449.70 ± 29.56 ab
Steam @ 90°C	0.100 ± 0.016 b	47.63 ± 2.18 bc	494.80 ± 51.49 ab
<i>Pr</i>	< 0.01	< 0.001	< 0.01
<i>LSD</i>	0.08	12.56	63.63

^a K_m , Michaelis constant; ^b V_{max} , maximum velocity; ^c $V_{max} K_m^{-1}$, catalytic efficiency

TABLE 4

Factors	$\Delta E^{\ddagger a}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H^{\ddagger b}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{\ddagger c}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S^{\ddagger d}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-T\Delta S^{\ddagger e}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Blanching (B)					
Water	41.41 ± 4.51 b	38.43 ± 2.85 b	100.50 ± 0.39	-0.173 ± 0.008 b	62.09 ± 2.89 a
Steam	53.93 ± 1.24 a	50.95 ± 0.79 a	101.40 ± 0.32	-0.141 ± 0.002 a	50.48 ± 0.88 b
<i>Pr</i>	< 0.10	< 0.01	< 0.001	< 0.01	< 0.01
<i>HSD</i>	9.97	11.10	-	0.031	11.18
Temperature (T)					
80°C (353.15°K)		44.74 ± 3.49	100.20 ± 0.24	-0.157 ± 0.009	55.45 ± 3.29
90°C (363.15°K)		44.65 ± 3.49	101.80 ± 0.17	-0.157 ± 0.009	57.11 ± 3.39
<i>Pr</i>		ns	< 0.001	ns	ns
<i>HSD</i>		-	-	-	-
Blanching (B) x Temperature (T)					
Water 80°C (353.15°K)		38.48 ± 4.51	99.65 ± 0.05 d	-0.173 ± 0.013	61.18 ± 4.46
Water 90°C (363.15°K)		38.39 ± 4.51	101.40 ± 0.08 b	-0.174 ± 0.013	62.99 ± 4.58
Steam 80°C (353.15°K)		51.00 ± 1.24	100.70 ± 0.03 c	-0.141 ± 0.004	49.73 ± 1.27
Steam 90°C (363.15°K)		50.91 ± 1.24	102.10 ± 0.06 a	-0.141 ± 0.004	51.22 ± 1.30
<i>Pr</i>		ns	< 0.05	ns	ns
<i>HSD</i>		-	0.257	-	-

^a ΔE^{\ddagger} , activation energy; ^b ΔH^{\ddagger} , activation enthalpy; ^c ΔG^{\ddagger} , activation Gibbs free energy; ^d ΔS^{\ddagger} , activation entropy; ^e $-T\Delta S^{\ddagger}$, normalised activation entropy.